

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

IV INTERNATIONAL SYMPOSIUM FOR AGRICULTURE AND FOOD

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9th Balkan Animal Sciences Conference BALNIMALCON 2022

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9th Balkan Animal Sciences Conference BALNIMALCON 2022

Organized by the
Faculty of Agricultural Sciences and Food - Skopje
Ss. Cyril and Methodius University in Skopje

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

In this Book of Abstracts you will find more than 250 abstracts classified in 10 thematic sections. The abstracts are published in their original form as provided by the authors. Double-blinded review will apply for the submitted full papers following the Instructions for Authors available at the ISAF 2022 web site. Looking forward to receive your full papers.

On behalf of the Secretariat of the 4th International Symposium for Agriculture and Food - ISAF 2022,

Ivana Janeska Stamenkovska
President of ISAF 2022 Secretariat

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NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT BY APPLICATION OF SMART TECHNOLOGIES IN WATER MANAGEMENT IN BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

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Abstract

In BiH, the S&T capacity and use of modern technologies in water management is limited, which causes a series of problems, including the inefficient use of natural resources, environmental burden and weak local economies. Promoting SMART agricultural WATER management in Bosnia and Herzegovina (SMARTWATER) is H2020 project, funded by the EC and coordinated by the University of Banja Luka (BiH). The main objectives are: 1) to reinforce the networking, research and innovation capacities of the University of Banja Luka (UNI-BL), University of Sarajevo (UNSA) and other BiH institutions in the field of sustainable agricultural water management and 2) to increase their competences and fund-rising skills for a successful participation in EU projects. SMARTWATER activities include: advanced courses, summer schools, joint research activities, staff exchanges, workshops and roundtable debates. The development and promotion of 2 smart water management tools (a DSS app for water management and a satellite tool) is also planned. The joint experimental activities started in 2021 at Aleksandrovac (UNI-BL) and Butmir (UNSA) sites in order to investigate maize crop productivity under different water and nitrogen treatments. UNI-BL, UNSA and other BiH institutions are particularly interested in reinforcing the networking and S&T capacity for optimizing the use of water, land, energy and fertilizers, by focusing on the development of modern irrigation methods and practices, and by applying the latest water management technologies and tools. We also promote climate change adaptation and mitigation strategies/measures and eco-efficiency as the main contemporary indicator of sustainability and rational use of natural resources.

Keywords: eco-efficiency, irrigation, networking, smart tools, SMARTWATER

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